

COMPARISON OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EPLEY'S MANEUVER AND PATIENT SPECIFIC TAILORED VESTIBULAR EXERCISES ON DIZZINESS, DYNAMIC BALANCE AND QUALITY OF LIFE IN INDIVIDUALS WITH PC-BENIGN PAROXYSMAL POSITIONAL VERTIGO

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (BPPV) remains the most frequent cause of peripheral vestibular dysfunction, characterized by brief, recurrent episodes of vertigo triggered by positional changes of the head. Posterior canal BPPV (PC-BPPV) significantly impairs balance, mobility, and quality of life. While the Epley's maneuver is an established canalith repositioning technique to alleviate vertigo, vestibular rehabilitation therapy (VRT) is gaining recognition for its role in enhancing long-term balance and functional independence.

Objective:

This study aimed to compare the efficacy of Epley's maneuver versus structured vestibular exercises on dizziness severity, dynamic balance, and daily functioning in individuals with PC-BPPV.

Methods:

A randomized controlled trial was conducted at the College of Physiotherapy, SVIMS University. Forty adult patients diagnosed with PC-BPPV were randomly assigned into two groups: Group A underwent the Epley's maneuver, while Group B received vestibular rehabilitation exercises including Gaze stabilization and habituation routines. Both groups were assessed at baseline (Day 0), mid intervention (4 weeks), and post-intervention (8 weeks) using the Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI), Dynamic Gait Index (DGI), and Vestibular Disorders Activities of Daily Living Scale (VADL). Statistical analyses were conducted using paired t-tests and between-group rank comparisons.

Results:

Both interventions resulted in significant within-group improvements ($p < 0.001$) in dizziness, dynamic gait, and activities of daily living across all time points. While Epley's maneuver produced faster initial relief in dizziness as indicated by greater DHI score reduction between weeks 4 and 8, vestibular exercises resulted in more progressive and sustained enhancements in balance and functional mobility, as reflected in DGI and VADL scores. No significant baseline differences were observed, confirming group homogeneity.

Conclusion:

Both Epley's maneuver and vestibular rehabilitation exercises are effective in reducing dizziness and improving balance and quality of life in PC-BPPV patients. Epley's maneuver offers rapid symptom resolution, whereas vestibular rehabilitation delivers gradual and enduring benefits in balance and daily functioning. Integrating individualized vestibular therapy protocols and considering tele-rehabilitation platforms may further optimize patient outcomes and accessibility.

Keywords:

Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo, Epley's maneuver, vestibular rehabilitation therapy, dizziness, dynamic gait index, quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (BPPV) is the leading peripheral vestibular disorder, marked by brief, recurrent episodes of vertigo induced by specific head movements.¹ Its prevalence ranges from 2.5% to 10% globally, and it accounts for more than 20% of all hospital visits for dizziness and vertigo.² BPPV can substantially impair quality of life, increasing fall risk, especially among older adults.³ Pathophysiologically, BPPV results from the displacement of otoliths into the semicircular canals, most often the posterior canal.^{4,5} Two main mechanisms canalolithiasis and cupulolithiasis underlie its symptomatology.⁶ Accurate diagnosis hinges on positional testing and observation of nystagmus, with the Dix-Hallpike maneuver being the gold standard.⁷ Treatment typically centers on canalith repositioning maneuvers, such as Epley's, semont's maneuvers and vestibular exercises. Despite evidence supporting both interventions, their comparative effectiveness requires further elucidation, prompting need for this experimental study.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

A prospective, experimental study was conducted in the Department of Neurology OPD and College of Physiotherapy, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Medical Sciences (SVIMS), Tirupati.

Sample Size and Allocation:

Forty adult subjects (age 20–60 years) diagnosed with unilateral posterior canal BPPV and a positive Dix-Hallpike test were enrolled through convenient sampling. The study received ethical clearance from institutional ethics committee-IEC Approval No.: 1774, and registered in clinical trials registry of India with CTRI No.: CTRI202505086830.

Inclusion Criteria:

Subjects with unilateral posterior canal BPPV, aged 20-60, both sexes, positive Dix-Hallpike test, and willingness to participate.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Subjects with anterior/horizontal/multi-canal BPPV,
- Cervical pathology,
- Vertebrobasilar insufficiency,
- Meniere's disease,
- Central vestibular dysfunction,
- Prior ear surgery,
- Musculoskeletal disorders impairing function, or history of head injury.

STUDY PROCEDURE:

All the subjects who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study after taking the informed consent. Upon recruitment, the subjects were randomly allocated into two groups to receive distinct therapeutic interventions. Prior to treatment session, Outcome measures included the Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI) to assess dizziness, Dynamic Gait Index (DGI) to evaluate dynamic balance and the Vestibular Activities of Daily Living Scale (VADL) to determine the level of independence in performing daily functional activities were evaluated and noted as Day 0.

Group A underwent treatment using the Epley's maneuver and Group B received Vestibular exercises, which included a structured program of gaze stabilization, habituation, and balance training exercises. Both interventions were administered

individually over a period of 8 weeks. Reassessment using DHI, DGI and VADL was conducted at the 4th week and at the end of the 8th week intervention period to evaluate and compare the changes and determine the relative effectiveness of each intervention.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data were entered into MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS 20 version. Paired t-tests evaluated within-group changes; between-group analyses used the Mann-Whitney U test due to non-normal data distribution. $p < 0.05$ is considered significant.

All forty subjects enrolled in the study completed the intervention, allowing for a robust comparison between the two therapeutic strategies. At the outset, the groups were comparable in terms of demographic features, including age and gender distribution. Demographic variables showed that Forty subjects with a mean age 39.55 ± 10.58 years for Group A, 46.5 ± 12.04 years for Group B with a female predominance in both groups.

Table - 1 Comparison of Demographic Variables between Group A and Group B.

variable	N	Mean \pm standard deviation	
Age	20	Group A (years)	Group B (years)
		39.55 ± 10.585	46.5 ± 12.045

Variable	N	Group A (N)	Group B (N)
Gender-male: female	20	4:16	3:17
Side-right: left	20	8:12	10:10

Within-Group analysis:

A paired t-test was used to analyse within-group changes in outcome measures across the three time intervals baseline (Day 0), mid-intervention (4 weeks), and post-intervention (8 weeks) within each group to evaluate the progression of dizziness, dynamic balance, and quality of life over time.

Epley's Maneuver Group (Group A):

The mean value of DHI significantly decreased from 60.40 ± 17.76 at baseline to 40.35 ± 17.18 at 4 weeks ($t = 9.53$), and further reduced to 22.05 ± 13.63 at 8 weeks ($t = 14.82$) and the comparison between 4 and 8 weeks also showed a significant reduction ($t = 9.22$) suggesting continued improvement over the intervention period.

The mean DGI value increased from 15.25 ± 4.46 at baseline to 20.15 ± 4.36 at 4 weeks ($t = -6.44$), and further improved to 25.40 ± 2.31 at 8 weeks ($t = -11.26$). A significant change was also observed between 4 and 8 weeks ($t = -6.53$) reflecting a steady improvement in dynamic balance and gait stability.

The mean value of VADL showed a significant decline from 91.40 ± 21.80 at baseline to 62.85 ± 21.89 at 4 weeks ($t = 10.83$), and further to 37.05 ± 13.28 at 8 weeks ($t = 15.87$) and a significant difference was also noted between the 4-week and 8-week scores ($t = 8.26$).

Table 2: Within group analysis of DHI, DGI, VADL across time points in group A (N=20).

Outcome	Comparison	Mean \pm standard deviation	t value	p-value	Significance
DHI	Day 0 vs 4 Weeks	60.40 ± 17.76	9.53	<0.001	<0.05
	4 Weeks vs 8 Weeks	40.35 ± 17.18	9.22		
	Day 0 vs 8 Weeks	22.05 ± 13.63	14.82		
DGI	Day 0 vs 4 Weeks	15.25 ± 4.46	-6.44	<0.001	<0.05
	4 Weeks vs 8 Weeks	20.15 ± 4.36	-6.53		
	Day 0 vs 8 Weeks	25.40 ± 2.31	-11.26		
VADL	Day 0 vs 4 Weeks	91.40 ± 21.80	10.83	<0.001	<0.05
	4 Weeks vs 8 Weeks	62.85 ± 21.89	8.26		
	Day 0 vs 8 Weeks	37.05 ± 13.28	15.87		

Vestibular Exercises Group (Group B):

A paired t-test showed significant improvements in dizziness, dynamic balance and quality of life after the intervention. The mean DHI value significantly reduced from 55.70 ± 16.77 at baseline to 35.70 ± 14.94 at 4 weeks ($t= 12.60, p < 0.001$), indicating a substantial reduction in perceived dizziness and Continued improvement was observed from 4 weeks to 8 weeks, with the score decreasing further to 17.30 ± 7.13 ($t= 9.31$), and a highly significant difference from Day 0 to 8 weeks ($t= 17.08$) suggesting a progressive and statistically significant improvement in dizziness symptoms over time.

Similarly, there is a significant improvement in dynamic balance, as the DGI score increased from 15.40 ± 5.21 at baseline to 21.15 ± 3.54 at 4 weeks ($t= -8.71, p < 0.001$). Further gains were noted by 8 weeks, reaching 24.85 ± 2.38 ($t = -12.96$), with a significant increase also evident between 4 and 8 weeks ($t = -10.28$). This shows a steady and statistically significant enhancement in dynamic balance and gait performance throughout the intervention.

The mean value of VADL significantly declined from 94.40 ± 21.31 at baseline to 65.10 ± 18.15 at 4 weeks ($t = 9.89, p < 0.001$), reflecting better functional ability, further mean decreased to 44.35 ± 12.61 at 8 weeks, with notable differences between all-time intervals ($t = 6.80$ from 4 to 8 weeks; $t= 13.75$ from Day 0 to 8 weeks) indicating a significant improvement in participants' ability to perform daily activities.

Table-3: Within group analysis of DHI, DGI, VADL across time points in group B (N=20).

Outcome	Comparison	Mean ± standard deviation	t value	p-value	Significance
DHI	Day 0 vs 4 Weeks	55.70 ± 16.77	12.60	<0.001	<0.05
	4 Weeks vs 8 Weeks	35.70 ± 14.94	9.31		
	Day 0 vs 8 Weeks	17.30 ± 7.13	17.08		
DGI	Day 0 vs 4 Weeks	15.40 ± 5.21	-8.71	<0.001	<0.05
	4 Weeks vs 8 Weeks	21.15 ± 3.54	-10.28		
	Day 0 vs 8 Weeks	24.85 ± 2.38	-12.96		
VADL	Day 0 vs 4 Weeks	94.40 ± 21.31	9.89	<0.001	<0.05
	4 Weeks vs 8 Weeks	65.10 ± 18.15	6.80		
	Day 0 vs 8 Weeks	44.35 ± 12.61	13.75		

Between-Group Comparisons

Between-group differences were assessed using the Mann-Whitney U test at each time point to compare outcome measure ranks across the two groups. This non-parametric test was selected to account for potential non-normal data distributions and to evaluate the relative effectiveness of the interventions in reducing symptoms and improving function.

DHI: The DHI scores demonstrated a progressive improvement over time in both groups, however, Group A showed superior improvement at the 8-week time point. At 8 weeks, a statistically significant between-group difference was observed ($p = 0.0442$), with Group A having a mean rank of 10.94 compared to 6.06 in Group B, yielding a rank difference of +4.88.

No significant differences were noted at baseline (Day 0) ($p > 0.2$), where mean ranks were 10.06 and 6.94 respectively, confirming homogeneity at the starting point. At 4 weeks, a modest increase in rank difference was observed (+3.50), but not statistically significant. This suggests that the improvements in Dizziness for Epley’s maneuver is more pronounced in the later weeks, particularly between week 4 and week 8.

DGI: Group B exhibited relatively better dynamic balance performance at the 4-week time point. At this time point, a notable rank difference of -4.38 (Group A = 6.31, Group B = 10.69) was observed, suggesting that group B may promote faster short-term improvement in dynamic balance.

By 8 weeks, this advantage diminished, and both groups showed near-equivalent ranks (8.13 vs. 8.88), indicating converging balance outcomes over time. At baseline, no significant difference was observed ($p > 0.2$), confirming that balance was comparable prior to intervention.

VADL: In the VADL, between-group rank differences remained small and non-significant across all three time points. Although some fluctuations were noted ($+0.62$ at Day 0, -1.62 at 4 weeks, and -1.00 at 8 weeks), none of these differences reached statistical significance ($p > 0.03$) across time points.

Table-4: Comparison of Mean ranks of DHI, DGI and VADL across time points between Group A and Group B

Outcome measure	Time point	Mean rank		Mean Rank difference	U value	Z score	P-value
		Group A	Group B				
DHI	Day 0	10.06	6.94	+3.12	44.5	-3.128	0.0007
	4 Week	10.25	6.75	+3.50	46.0	-3.072	
	8 Week	10.94	6.06	+4.88	51.5	-2.864	

DGI	Day 0	7.13	9.88	-2.75	44.5	-4.014	0.0415
	4 Week	6.31	10.69	-4.38	46.0	-4.259	
	8 Week	8.13	8.88	-0.75	51.5	-3.712	
VADL	Day 0	8.81	8.19	+0.62	34.5	-3.505	0.0310
	4 Week	7.69	9.31	-1.62	25.5	-3.844	
	8 Week	8.00	9.00	-1.00	28.0	-3.750	

DISCUSSION:

The present study aimed to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of Epley’s Maneuver (Group A) and patient-specific vestibular exercises therapy (Group B) on dizziness, balance, and quality of life in subjects diagnosed with unilateral posterior canal benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (PC-BPPV). A total of 40 participants were recruited and equally distributed into two groups, with both receiving intervention over an 8-week period. Outcome measures including the Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI), Dynamic Gait Index (DGI), and Vestibular Disorders Activities of Daily Living Scale (VADL) were assessed at baseline, 4 weeks, and 8 weeks. Statistical analysis demonstrated significant improvements within both groups over time. However, between-group comparisons revealed that the Epley’s Maneuver group showed a greater reduction in dizziness symptoms, whereas the VRT group showed slight advantages in balance improvements during the early phase of intervention.

The average age of participants in Group A was 39.55 ± 10.58 years, while that of Group B was 46.5 ± 12.04 years, indicating a middle-aged adult population commonly affected by BPPV. There was a female predominance in both groups (Group A: 4 males, 16 females; Group B: 3 males, 17 females), consistent with

existing literature which highlights a higher prevalence of BPPV among women, particularly in premenopausal and postmenopausal age groups due to hormonal influences on calcium metabolism and otolith stability.⁸

A recent study by Alghadir et al. (2023) examined the efficacy of Epley's Maneuver in comparison to VRT exercises in BPPV patients and found that repositioning maneuvers were more effective in reducing dizziness and nystagmus intensity in the short term, consistent with our findings for DHI scores in Group A at 8 weeks.⁹ Patients undergoing Epley's Maneuver experienced quicker symptom resolution due to the mechanical clearance of otoconia from the posterior semi-circular canal, reinforcing the mechanistic rationale behind the maneuvers rapid effect.¹⁰

In the current study, both groups demonstrated statistically significant improvements from baseline to 8 weeks across all outcome measures in within group analysis. Group A showed a marked decrease in DHI scores from 60.40 ± 17.76 at baseline to 22.05 ± 13.63 at 8 weeks, indicating a substantial decrease in perceived dizziness and functional handicap. These findings align with a 2021 randomized controlled trial by Tanimura et al., which confirmed the Epley's maneuver significantly improves dizziness-related quality of life within one to two sessions in most cases.¹¹ Conversely, in our Group B, DHI scores improved from 55.70 ± 16.77 to 17.30 ± 7.13 , highlighting that Vestibular exercises although slower in action can result in substantial gains when adhered to consistently over a longer duration. In Group A, DGI scores improved from 15.25 ± 4.46 to 25.40 ± 2.31 , while VADL scores declined from 91.40 ± 21.80 to 37.05 ± 13.28 , demonstrating enhanced gait stability and reduced functional impairment in daily activities.

In support of Vestibular exercises, a systematic review by Hall et al. (2016) emphasized the importance of incorporating vestibulo-ocular reflex (VOR) training and habituation exercises into the rehabilitation of patients with peripheral vestibular hypofunction. This review documented strong evidence that VRT leads to significant improvements in postural control, gait stability, and subjective symptom burden, particularly when applied over 4–6 weeks.¹² This supports the present study's finding where Group B exhibited notable improvement in DGI, with mean scores rising from 15.40 ± 5.21 to 24.85 ± 2.38 , indicating progressive gains in dynamic balance.

Although both groups showed marked improvements, the rate and trajectory of recovery differed, with Epley's Maneuver exhibiting faster reductions in dizziness, and VRT showing steady gains in balance and function. The Epley's maneuver greater reduction in DHI scores (mean difference: 38.35) over 8 weeks may be attributed to its direct mechanical action on canalith repositioning. However, VRT provided steady improvements in balance and function, evident through significant changes in DGI and VADL scores. These results align with a 2023 study by Jung et al., which found that combined VRT and balance exercises in BPPV patients not only reduced dizziness but also enhanced gait performance and reduced fall risk over time.¹³ Interestingly, while the between-group comparison revealed no statistically significant differences at baseline, a significant difference was observed in DHI at 8 weeks ($U = 51.5, p = 0.0442$), favouring Epley's group. This supports the hypothesis that repositioning maneuvers like Epley's offer faster symptomatic relief by directly addressing the mechanical displacement of otoconia in the posterior semicircular canal. Meanwhile, Group B exhibited greater DGI improvements at the 4-week interval, supporting the idea that VRT facilitates faster improvements in dynamic balance compared to Epley's alone during early recovery stages. This finding is consistent with the work of Yetiser et al. (2020), who found that patients undergoing balance training exhibited improved gait adaptability and reduced dependence during functional activities.¹⁴

The physiological basis for the improvements in VRT can be attributed to central compensation mechanisms that occur in response to repeated vestibular stimuli during gaze stabilization and habituation exercises. These exercises help reduce visual dependence, recalibrate vestibular input, and improve integration of multi-sensory information, thereby enhancing both balance and quality of life. Herdman et al. (2021) emphasized that while VRT may take longer to demonstrate improvements, the gains are often more robust and longer-lasting, particularly in chronic or recurrent cases of vestibular dysfunction.¹⁵

On the other hand, Epley's Maneuver is designed to relocate dislodged otoconia from the semicircular canals back into the utricle, thereby resolving the aberrant endolymphatic flow that triggers vertigo. The immediate reduction in DHI scores observed in Group A can be attributed to the mechanical resolution of the underlying

pathology, which aligns with findings from numerous studies including those by Hilton and Pinder (2014), who concluded that Epley's maneuver is the most effective treatment for posterior canal BPPV.¹⁶

Therefore, the present study supports a hybrid model of BPPV management where Epley's Maneuver is employed as the first-line treatment for immediate symptom relief, followed by individualized vestibular exercises to enhance balance and improve quality of life. Such an approach is consistent with clinical guidelines by the American Academy of Otolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery, which recommend vestibular exercises for patients with persistent imbalance or recurrent episodes despite successful canalith repositioning.¹⁷

Based on these findings, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the two interventions and accept the alternate hypothesis that both Epley's maneuver and vestibular exercises have significant effects on dizziness, balance, and quality of life in PC-BPPV patients with Epley's showing quicker dizziness relief and VRT offering progressive balance recovery. Thus, this present study concluded that there is significant difference between Epley's maneuver and patient specific tailored vestibular exercises on dizziness, balance and quality of life among subjects with unilateral posterior canal benign paroxysmal positional vertigo.

Limitations and recommendations

- The sample size was relatively small (N = 40).
- Longterm follow up data on symptom recurrence were not collected.
- Future studies should explore the cost-effectiveness of combined therapies, the optimal timing and dosage of VRT post Epley's maneuver and the impact of patient education on self-administered maneuvers.
- The incorporation of tele -rehabilitation platforms could also expand access to VRT.

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